

Editorial

Abdulsalam Ibraheem Rafida: Sorrow for Your Loss

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On April 10, 2021, colleges, friends, and students of University of Tripoli were shocked by news of death of **Abdulsalam Ibraheem Rafida**, Professor of Analytical Chemistry at Faculty of Medical Technology, the University of Tripoli. He died in a Turkey hospital after a short struggle with leukemia and bone marrow cancer, with subsequent Covid-19 infection, caused Severe Respiratory Distress Syndrome (SARS).

Professor Abdulsalam was born in Tripoli on January 27, 1962. He obtained his BSc in 1984 and MBBS in 1994 from the University of Tripoli. He received his PhD in 2006 from University of Newcastle upon Tyne, UK. His PhD thesis in environmental biotechnology was on the removal of heavy metals in vertical flow biofilters conditioned with sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB).

On his return to Libya, he set as head of Pathology Department at Faculty of Medical Technology, University

of Tripoli (2008-2009), and started teaching the subject of public health and environment health.

On 2014, Professor Abdulsalam had joined the University of Tripoli Alahlia in Janzur, and established two Medical departments; Pharmacy and Medical laboratories, and appointed as founding member of the scientific committee and quality assurance team of these departments. He became the head of Scientific Research and International Cooperation at the University of Tripoli Alahlia (2017–2020) of which he was a founding member and counselor.

Professor Abdulsalam involved in many teaching and research activities. He has published more than 10 articles in peer-reviewed journals, and one book entitled water; characteristics, specification, and pollutes. He is one of the co-founders and advisory members of AlQalam Journal of Medical and Applied Sciences – AJMAS (eISSN: 2707-7179).

The characteristic of his personality was expressed not only in his work but also in his personal experiences at scientific and administrative meetings throughout the university. He was a caring friend who shared his colleagues' joys and sorrows, counseled them on their future plans, and provided them with opportunities. He was compassionate and kind, always surprising friends and coworkers with gifts and memories.

Abdulsalam will be remembered for dedicating his professional life to enhancing research at our faculty and university. His family, friends, and colleagues in Libya will definitely miss him.